

CLINICAL AND LABORATORY EVALUATION OF OZONE THERAPY IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH INFECTIOUS-INFLAMMATORY PLACENTAL DYSFUNCTION

M.A. Kamolova

A.V. An

Tashkent State Medical University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19199410>

Abstract: Infectious-inflammatory placental dysfunction is one of the leading causes of complicated pregnancy, associated with impaired microcirculation, activation of systemic inflammatory response, and disturbances in the hemostatic system. These changes are reflected in laboratory abnormalities, including anemia, inflammatory markers, and hypercoagulation, which indicate the severity of the pathological process and dysfunction of the mother-placenta-fetus system. Standard treatment approaches do not always ensure sufficient correction of these disorders, which necessitates the search for more effective therapeutic strategies. Ozone therapy is considered a promising adjunct due to its anti-inflammatory, antihypoxic, and rheological effects.

Object: To evaluate the clinical and laboratory effectiveness of ozone therapy as part of комплекс treatment in pregnant women with infectious-inflammatory placental dysfunction.

Materials and Methods. A comparative study included 125 pregnant women at 22–28 weeks of gestation. The main group consisted of 100 pregnant women with placental dysfunction, divided into two subgroups (n=50 each). Group I received standard therapy combined with ozone therapy, while Group II received standard treatment only. The control group included 25 healthy pregnant women. General blood parameters, hemostasis indices, and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were assessed before and after treatment.

Results. Before treatment, both subgroups demonstrated signs of anemia, inflammatory response, and hypercoagulation. Following therapy, positive dynamics were observed in both groups; however, they were more pronounced in the ozone therapy group. Hemoglobin levels increased to 104.8 g/L in Group I compared to 99.6 g/L in Group II. A more significant reduction in leukocytosis and erythrocyte sedimentation rate was observed. Hemostatic parameters showed more pronounced normalization in Group I, including a decrease in fibrinogen levels, normalization of the prothrombin index, and prolongation of activated partial thromboplastin time. CRP levels decreased by 67.9% in Group I compared to 54.4% in Group II.

Conclusions. The inclusion of ozone therapy in treatment of pregnant women with infectious-inflammatory placental dysfunction leads to more pronounced improvement in laboratory parameters, better normalization of hemostasis, and a greater reduction in systemic inflammatory activity. These findings support the clinical effectiveness of ozone therapy as an adjunctive component in the management of this condition.